

Communication Techniques in Environmental Campaigns: Creating a Species Awareness Campaign in Malta

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Authorship Statement

This composition and based on the results of research carried out by myself, is my own composition, and has not been previously presented for any other certified or uncertified qualification.

The research was carried out under the supervision of Mr Adolf Formosa.

Signed

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Abstract

This dissertation focuses on environmental campaigns, which aim to change public perceptions and behaviours on ecological issues. It explores the visuals, techniques, and frameworks used in these campaigns through secondary research. These factors are further explored through case studies. Then information on local species, local environmental campaigns and target audiences was gathered through interviews with local environmental organisations. This was done in an attempt to identify the most effective methods for conserving local wildlife on the Maltese islands. The result culminated in, Blossoms of Heritage, a project which aims to raise awareness of threatened plant species on the Maltese islands. This also serves as both a celebration of their beauty and a call to action for preservation.

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1 Introduction

This dissertation study focuses on environmental campaigns. An environmental campaign aims at changing public perceptions and behaviours on an ecological issue. This study explores the visuals, techniques and frameworks used in such campaigns. It aims to find the most effective methods to create a campaign to conserve local wildlife on the Maltese islands.

The topic of environmental campaigns was selected due to a strong affinity for the natural world and a general interest in environmental graphics. The primary motivation for this research was to create more purposeful work and utilize graphic design skills to promote animal and nature conservation. This study holds significant importance for designers, as it is essential for them to understand which visuals and communication techniques effectively raise awareness and encourage support for environmental issues. The findings will guide in framing messages to achieve maximum campaign impact.

Beyond the design community, this study is also valuable to locals, activists, and policymakers. Through in-depth interviews, the research highlights local environmental issues and suggests ways to address and support these concerns. Effective environmental campaigns are crucial for raising awareness and driving environmental change locally, making this study important for society.

This study starts with the literature review, which explores the visual techniques and frameworks used in environmental campaigns. It evaluates the types of visuals employed, the messages these visuals convey, the issue-framing

methods utilized, and which techniques are most successful at creating awareness and garnering support for environmental campaigns.

The primary research is split into two parts, case studies and interviews. In the first part, some case studies were conducted on international environmental campaigns to find out factors such as the target audience, the platforms used, the content created and an analysis of visuals. The visual analysis examines colours, typography, style, and overall feel. Through these case studies, an insight into how visuals and communication techniques are applied to different environmental campaigns was gained. The second part of the primary research consists of interviews conducted with local environmental organizations and NGOs. These were done to gather more information on local environmental campaigns. Here information on local threatened species, past environmental campaigns and target audience was gathered. Ultimately, the project culminates in the creation of an environmental campaign aimed at conserving species on the Maltese Islands, called Blossoms of Heritage.

2 Review of Literature on Environmental Campaigns

2.1 Introduction

An environmental campaign is a type of awareness campaign with the aim of changing public perceptions and behaviours on an environmental issue. This study explores the visuals, techniques and frameworks used in such campaigns. It aims to find the most effective methods to create an environmental campaign to conserve local wildlife on the Maltese islands.

This research first starts by defining an awareness campaign. Then it outlines the effectiveness of images in environmental communication. It follows by mentioning what imagery is used in endangered animal-related campaigns. After that, it introduces the seven main topics in endangered animal-related campaigns. Finally, it moves on to the next half where it introduces frameworks and communication techniques suitable for environmental campaigns and mentions the impact of semiotics in campaigns. Finally, it concludes with a presentation of the study's findings.

2.1.1 Definition of Awareness Campaign

An awareness campaign is viewed as a type of communication or a marketing campaign, from the semiotics perspective, and is referred to as social advertising or social marketing (Park et al., 2004, as cited in Vallverdu-Gordi & Marine-Roig, 2023). Unlike typical marketing initiatives, this one raises awareness and encourages the public to alter their behaviour on specific social and/or

environmental issues and is not intended to encourage a purchase or to increase brand loyalty (Borawska, 2017; Peverini, 2014 as cited in *ibid*).

2.2 Visuals in Environmental Campaigns

2.2.1 The Effectiveness of Images in Environmental Communication

Images have several benefits which make using them to engage the audience with a topic crucial, mostly when presenting new or challenging concepts, such as environmental ones. One of these benefits is them being more appealing than text (O'Neill, 2013, cited in Gulliver, et al., 2020), as visuals are the first thing individuals focus on when viewing communication content, according to research on eye-tracking and brain imaging (Domke, Et al., 2002, cited in Gulliver, et al., 2020). Moreover, the processing of images is quicker than text and can impact the audiences' views by altering how they digest the subject matter emotionally and intellectually (Hart & Feldman, 2016; Thatcher, Et al., 2018 cited in Gulliver, et al., 2020).

Images also have traits that facilitate communicating information. They help people memorise information, can give clear and emotive depictions which can captivate audiences and can overcome geographical and linguistic constraints. Besides that, Images, particularly photographs are “seen as a direct representation of reality, rather than viewed as a particular version of reality framed in a particular way”, explained O'Neill and Smith, (2014) and thus they are viewed as a representation of the truth. On the other hand, unlike verbal language, images lack the use of a precise syntax to make connections and propositions. Thus, other

imprecise indicators must be used. This makes it harder to show the sequence of an event and can lead to misinterpretation (O'Neill & Smith, 2014).

Although imagery can be very powerful, sometimes it is not effective enough on its own. An example of this can be seen in the study conducted by Olesen (2018 cited in Gulliver, et al., 2020) where the intention to participate in collaborative efforts in helping refugees was assessed using visuals of refugees suffering. Although images did generate emotional reactions, researchers discovered that these reactions were insufficient to significantly change participants' willingness to engage in political engagement activities. Thus, images in campaigns should be combined with text. According to studies about the effects of imagery on climate change communication, image manipulation can influence how effectively and how important an issue is perceived (O'Neill, 2013, cited in Gulliver, et al., 2020).

2.2.2 The Imagery Used in Endangered Animal-Related Campaigns

Furthermore, Su Wenjun's research analysed the visuals of 312 endangered animal-related campaigns for public education using the scaling method (2019). The findings from this research show that most of the analysed campaigns have a negative image ambience, showing hopelessness and misery regarding the future of endangered animals. Furthermore, 74.96% of the campaigns' suggested visual depictions of the link between humans and nature, show conflicting relationships between the two. Therefore, Wenjun (2019) concluded that "negative visual image by creating a conflicting relationship between humans and nature is the mainstream communication strategy in endangered animal-related campaigns." In addition to

the above, out of the 312 campaigns, 66.99% contained violence as a main visual motif, while 83.01% detailed or implied negative human images. This concludes that two common methods for producing a negative image ambience and conflicting relationships are using elements of violence and negative human images (Wenjun, 2019).

The topics of endangered animal-related use in Wenjun's (2019) research are various and were arranged into 7 categories. The main 3 categories were wildlife poaching/trade, habitat destruction and the promotion of endangered animals. Global climate change, predatory fishing, plastic pollution, and others (desertification, fur business, meat production, compound issues and animal shows) are the other minor 4 categories. It was seen that from these categories, the main 3 have been around for the longest period due to illegal poaching and habitat loss being the most threatening factors to endangered animals, which for a long time has been shown through conservation research (Wenjun, 2019).

2.3 Frameworks and Communication Techniques Suitable for Environmental Campaigns

2.3.1 Issue-Framing for Environmental Campaigns

Regarding issue-framing methods, research done in 2019 by Nicolas M. Anspach and Gorana Draguljić, investigated how using different psychological moderators influences the impact of environmental campaigns generating support. This study examines the motivational, economic, and personal frames, using

personal efficacy, psychological proximity, and emotion as psychological moderators.

Motivational frameworks stress the power of the audience to bring about change (Benford and Snow 2000 as cited in Anspach & Draguljić, 2019). Economic frameworks make use of people's self-interest to try and close the psychological gap or to arouse emotion by emphasizing the issue's detrimental financial impact (Corner et al. 2018; Kuhne and Schemer 2017 as cited in *ibid.*) Personal frames seek to eliminate psychological distance by using specific individuals to make the issue's consequences relatable and to elicit emotions of rage and sadness through the recounting of the victims' experiences (Slovic 2007; Kuhne and Schemer 2017 as cited *ibid.*).

This study found that motivational frameworks are the least effective as they fail to inspire the audience with a sense of power or evoke endorsement of the campaign. Comparatively, the psychological distance is reduced through the economic and personal frames, which both provoke anger and sadness. As a result, people are more likely to report supporting the campaign through these frames. Moreover, this research's data shows that the best psychological motivators for behavioural change are sadness and the reduction of psychological distance, both of which significantly boost people's support for the campaign. This research concludes that motivational frameworks should be avoided and that emphasizing the detrimental effects that environmental issues have on people's lives is likely to make a campaign successful (Anspach & Draguljić, 2019).

2.3.2 Communication Techniques Suitable for Environmental Campaigns

Besides issue-framing methods, there are also other communication techniques which are suitable for environmental campaigns which can inspire and foster change. A common technique is using stories as they evoke emotion and consequently create impact. In his TEDx Talk, John Spencer (2023) suggests using butterfly stories. “Butterfly stories are stories of hope, optimism [and] about the future of our planet” (ibid.). Such stories create the butterfly story effect, meaning they inspire people and foster positive environmental change (TEDx Talks, 2023).

Another technique suggested by John Marshall on the Outrage + Optimism podcast (2023), is to mention the consequences of an environmental issue within six words after mentioning the issue’s name. This is because the environmental issue is an issue in the first place due to its problematic consequences. Therefore, people should feel like they are fighting the consequences rather than the issue itself. Marshall also suggested using humanity, simplicity and accountability: “Keep it simple, make it about humans[,] ... identify the source of the problem and communicate that right away” (Figueres, Rivett-Carnac, & Dickinson, 2023).

The 3As framework is another appropriate communication technique. As explained by Renee Lertzman during a Creatives for Climate learning event (2023), the 3As framework focuses on addressing anxieties, ambivalence, and aspirations within environmental campaigns, instead of immediately jumping to the aspirations. This can be achieved by attuning to the target audience’s anxieties and ambivalence. Affirming and acknowledging all the 3As will increase credibility. As

Lertzman addresses it, “People will really gain trust and traction with you if we name and acknowledge what’s hard” (2023).

An example she mentioned was how Transport for London wanted people to use more bikes. Their ad campaigns consisted of having a bike with flowers all over it. This communicated poorly as it only showed the aspirations but ignored the anxieties of getting killed by a bike, getting wet in the rain and the ambivalence of also wanting to get on a bike. She then explained how this can be shown using the 3As. This is by showing someone on a bike in the rain who although is wet is very excited (Creatives for Climate, 2023).

Punctuation can also be used as a tool for better communication. As mentioned by Sheila Levrant de Bretteville during a Walker Art Center (2018) talk, the use of punctuation marks, such as question marks and ellipses, is a good way to foster reflection and discussion. This technique engages the viewers through indirect participation (Walker Art Center, 2018).

2.3.3 The Application of Persuasion Theory

In the Journal of Social Issues, Bator and Cialdini (2000) talk about the lack of usage of persuasion research in the making of pro-environmental messages. Here they provide guidelines which can significantly boost behavioural change in such campaigns. A lot of research they found, emphasized on identifying the target audience, their attitudes, and behaviours towards the issue, “and then pilot testing responses to preliminary versions of the message” stated Bator and Cialdini (2000).

Mendelsohn (1973), drawing on prior research, discovered 3 factors which elevate a public information campaign's probability of success. The first factor is that the campaign developers anticipate that most audiences are moderately interested in the message. The second one is that the developers are convinced that basic exposure to the message leads to the behavioural change or information gain desired. The last factor is that a detailed analysis of the audience's values, habits with mass media, lifestyles and demographics is conducted. Atkin and Freimuth (1989), assert that "evaluation research should first answer questions about audience attitudes and behaviors [sic] prior to the campaign design, then evaluate the design's execution and effectiveness during and after a campaign".

2.3.4 The Impact of Semiotics in Campaigns

In the early stages of any communication project, verbal and non-verbal elements are combined to influence the experience of the audience (Echtner, 1999 as cited in Vallverdu-Gordi & Marine-Roig, 2023). From the perspective of semiotics, graphic design is viewed as a tool that may produce signs and reactions to these signs that arise from the public's perceptions while utilizing visual components, such as colours, shapes, typography, and so on.

"Semiotics can be defined as the science of signs and of the construction of meaning that is linked to the production and circulation of signs. Signs are all types of entities that have or can have meaning for someone. Signs can be produced and spread voluntarily, as in the case of words, images, gestures, [and so on], or non-voluntarily,

including elements of the natural world that are interpreted by someone as meaningful" (Catellani, 2022).

That is, applied semiotics employ knowledge of signs to accomplish goals like changing consumer behaviour (Marine-Roig, E., 2021. As cited in Vallverdu-Gordi & Marine-Roig, 2023).

The target audience is the agent of semiotics. Therefore, the cultural and historical context of the location where the information is shared substantially influences the meanings and interpretations given to signs. Moreover, the study of the visual and linguistic signs that a visual communication product uses allows researchers to understand and foresee the behaviour of their target audience toward that visual communication product (Echtner, 1999 as cited in Vallverdu-Gordi & Marine-Roig, 2023).

"In advertising the signification of the image is undoubtedly intentional; the signifieds of the advertising message are formed a priori by certain attributes of the product and these signifieds have to be transmitted as clearly as possible. If the image contains signs, we can be sure that in advertising these signs are full, formed with a view to the optimum reading: the advertising image is frank, or at least emphatic." (Barthes, 1997)

2.4 Conclusion

This study's objective is to explore the visuals, frameworks and communication techniques used in environmental campaigns and compile the most effective methods one should use to create a successful one. As mentioned in the

literature review, an environmental campaign is a type of awareness campaign which aims to change public perceptions and behaviours on an environmental issue. Through this research, it was discovered that images with text are most effective when combined in an environmental campaign and that photographs are seen as the truth. Furthermore, sadness and the reduction of psychological distance can highly increase the public's support for a campaign. There are vast communication techniques which when applied to an environmental campaign help make it effective. Research on the target audience is key to successful campaigns. It was also noted that the good application of semiotics is essential in getting the desired results from a campaign. These findings tie in with this study as they reveal research on what has already been done on this topic and serve as a compilation of best practices when curating an environmental campaign.

3 Gathering More Insights

The methodology begins with case studies of international environmental campaigns, analysing target audiences, platforms, content, and visuals. The campaigns studied include FEEDitBag by Edeka, Endangered Love by Wildlife Conservation Film Festival, and WWF: Eurythenes Plasticus by BBDO Berlin. Insights were gained on the use of visuals and communication techniques in these campaigns. Subsequently, interviews were conducted with various environmental organizations and NGOs, including the Environment and Resources Authority, BirdLife Malta, Friends of the Earth Malta, ACT Malta, Nature Trust Malta, and Grow 10 Trees. These interviews focused on threatened species, local campaigns, and target audiences, providing valuable insights. The methodology concludes by summarizing the findings from the case studies and interviews, explaining how this information assisted in creating a species awareness campaign in Malta, and introduces the dissertation project 'Blossoms of Heritage'.

3.1 Researching Foreign Environmental Campaigns through Case Studies

3.1.1 FEEDitBAG by Edeka – The First Plastic Bag that Gives Life

The first campaign analysed to understand more about the visuals and communication techniques of environmental campaigns was FEEDitBAG by Edeka. FEEDitBAG is an initiative taken by Edeka, a German supermarket company, with the aim to go beyond using paper and cloth bags to fight plastic pollution. This initiative involves offering customers biodegradable bags with seeds

on them, to put their fruits and vegetables in when shopping. This incentive not only eliminates plastic bags from the organic section but also allows users to throw their organic scraps into the bag and plant them to grow their own fruit and vegetables at home (Campaigns of the World, 2022).

This initiative's target audience is consumers who mainly shop for fruits and vegetables. It was promoted through online posts and a video and used platforms such as Facebook and a project website, which is currently unavailable. Its posts include images of the bags, videos promoting the bags and posts showing the concept and how the bags are used.

Regarding visuals, FEEDitBAG uses 2 watercolour-like, hand-written script typefaces in its main typography and a simple sans serif for wordy information. The bags use realistic images of fruit and vegetables, which were probably drawn digitally. The typefaces and graphical elements use black and a dark shade of the colour of the fruit or vegetable on the bag. This visual style gives the bags an earthy feel which goes well with the initiative.

feedit bag

THE FIRST PLASTIC BAG THAT GIVES LIFE

reduce Plastic grow Food

feedit bag

COLLECTING ORGANIC WASTE

COMPOSTING FEEDITBAG

GROWING NEW LIFE

EACH BAG COMES WITH SEEDS TO GROW FRUITS AND VEGGIES

PROBLEM There are plenty alternatives to plastic shopping bags, but the thin plastic bags for fruits and vegetables aren't going away anytime soon. They are still used by the billion and each pollutes our nature for up to 500 years!

IDEA We developed the first plastic bag that gives life instead of taking it: FEEDITBAG is not only bio-degradable in 10 weeks - it even grows food with integrated seeds.

PRODUCT The bag is made of Mater-Bi, which is based on renewable resources and printed with water-based colours. All components, from bag to sticker are 100% bio-degradable, even in water. The tasty illustrations make you hunger for the food that you can grow. This way, FEEDITBAG doesn't only reduce the plastic waste, it also gives something back to nature.

SCHECK-IN CENTER EDEKA

Figure 1: Description of initiative (Campaigns of the World, 2022).

Figure 2: An image of the main 3 bags produced (Campaigns of the World, 2022).

Figure 3: Two promotional posters used on FEEDitBAG's Facebook page.

3.1.2 Wildlife Conservation Film Festival: Endangered Love

The next environmental campaign that was analysed for these case studies was Endangered Love. This campaign was created for WCFF to engage youths and raise money for endangered species such as gorillas, rhinos, sloths, and pandas. This campaign uses a humorous approach to reach its goals by using illustrations of the mentioned endangered species engaging in sex. This campaign was first launched through an animated video using pandas singing a remake of the song 'I Just Had Sex (feat. Akon)' by The Lonely Island (Hurwitz, 2016).

This branding campaign consisted of print, out-of-home and social media to lead individuals to the campaign's website. There, individuals could buy branded items such as artwork, clothes, accessories, and books. Gained profits then went to WCFF to help them with their conservation efforts (ibid.).

The campaign branding involves a mix of bold and pastel colours for a youthful feel. The typefaces used are a regular sans serif and a Bold sans serif used in all caps for headings. It uses illustrations in a detailed, cartoon-like style, with a lot of drawn-on texture which makes the concept fun but also a bit mature. The main illustrations are also artistically framed in an outlined border. The branding of this concept addresses their target audience well, through their use of vibrant colours, illustration style and humorous undertone.

Figure 4: 3 of the posters created for this campaign.

Figure 5: The panda poster created for this campaign.

Figure 6: Some merchandise created for this campaign.

3.1.3 WWF: Eurythenes Plasticus by BBDO Berlin

The last case study conducted to analyse the visuals and communication techniques in environmental campaigns was WWF's Eurythenes Plasticus by BBDO Berlin. Alexander Nicolas (2020) explained how this environmental campaign started after a new deep-sea species was discovered with PET plastic in its body. Thus, scientists decided to name this species Eurythenes Plasticus to embody the extent that the plastic problem has become. On the 5th of March, they started their campaign and made history by adding Eurythenes Plasticus to the taxonomic record of our planet. "Within hours of the ZOOTAXA [zoology journal's] publication, a worldwide conversation had ignited over the extent of the plastic pollution in our oceans in over forty countries without any media spend" explained WWF (n.d.).

After this action, WWF created a cross-platform campaign which included, printed posters with the scientific manuscript, a digital flight-enhanced campaign and a cinema spot. They also created educational and interactive ads which used the pitch, play, and plunge principle; driving conversation. All of these actions were used to urge people to sign their petition to end ocean plastic pollution through a UN law (ibid.). The visual style of this campaign is very serious and clean as to represent its scientific background. The imagery shown is mainly photographs of the species. Typography uses a combination of a neat serif typeface and a neat sans serif typeface; the latter being used in all caps. Graphical elements use the campaign's colours which are white and yellow. This campaign does not specify a target audience.

Figure 7: Main visual from the Eurythenes Plasticus campaign (Clio Awards, 2020).

Figure 8: Shots from the interactive game created for this campaign (WWF, n.d.).

Figure 9: Picture from the video pitch from the campaign (WWF, n.d.).

3.2 Researching Local Environmental Campaigns through Interviews

Following the previous section analysing foreign campaigns, interviews were conducted with local environmental NGOs and organisations to find more information on local environmental campaigns. Here they were asked questions on local species, past environmental campaigns, and the target audience. The interviewed organisations are the Environment and Resources Authority, BirdLife Malta, Friends of the Earth Malta, ACT Malta, Nature Trust Malta, and Grow 10 Trees.

3.2.1 Interview with the Environment and Resources Authority (ERA)

The first interview was with Malta's Environment and Resources Authority (ERA). They identified human intervention, particularly development, as the main threat to species endangerment. To protect local species, ERA emphasized the need for increased awareness about local and national species and the importance of not abandoning pets in the wild, as they can become invasive alien species (ERA, 2024).

ERA mentioned that their current campaigns focus on invasive alien species and local habitats. Invasive alien species are species which "are introduced in our local environment from abroad and from other environments and they are a threat to our local species" (ERA, 2024). They are also involved in an EU-funded project, the Corallo, which is about the conservation and awareness of marine protected areas. In previous years they had campaigns on the Natura 2000 sites. Besides

campaigns ERA also creates laws, public events, and signage to areas like Natura 2000 sights; to protect and educate people when visiting these sites.

When asked about the success of their campaigns, ERA highlighted that using the theme of biodiversity helped create visually appealing materials, like videos and static designs, which attracted attention. They noted that people can relate more to animals and plants, as environmental awareness grows. However, they also mentioned that technical topics were harder for the public to understand, posing a disadvantage. ERA emphasized that good research and a targeted marketing plan are essential for effective environmental campaigns. They highlighted the importance of creativity in design but stressed that planning is equally crucial. While ERA aims to reach a broad audience, it primarily focuses on targeting youths, believing that young people are increasingly environmentally conscious and knowledgeable about ensuring a bright future and quality of life (ibid.).

3.2.2 Interview with BirdLife Malta (BLM)

The second interview was with BirdLife Malta, which emphasized the need for increased conservation efforts to protect the European Turtle Dove, an endangered species hunted during spring in Malta. BirdLife Malta has conducted 2 to 3 campaigns on this species, both locally and internationally. They highlighted the Turtle Dove as symbolic of their efforts to protect migrating birds in the Maltese Islands, identifying illegal hunting as the main threat. Additionally, they noted that seabirds also deserve more attention (BirdLife Malta, 2024).

In fact, BirdLife Malta along with other international BirdLife members, such as Spea (BirdLife Portugal), Hellenic Ornithological Society (BirdLife Greece), SEO (BirdLife Spain) and other partners, are currently embarking on a project called 'Life PanPuffinus'. Locally in this project, they are focusing on the Yelkouan Shearwater as this species' numbers are dwindling. The main threat mentioned for this species is rat predation as the Yelkouan Shearwater only produces one egg a year. Thus: "If this egg or the fledgling which is the chick, is predated by rats while it is still hatching, the Yelkouan Shearwater has lost its only egg for that year (BirdLife Malta, 2024)." To combat this, BirdLife Malta campaigns to educate the public on not leaving trash near species' colonies, particularly in areas like 'I-Irdum tal-Madonna' and Comino, as picnic rubbish fuels rat infestations. The second major issue is bycatch, where birds get entangled in fishing nets or swallow hooks. To address this, BirdLife Malta engages with fishermen using manuals, guidelines, and signs in key locations like 'I-Irdum tal-Madonna', the cliffs, or 'Ta' Ċenċ' in Gozo, and meetings to teach proper methods to prevent bycatch (ibid.).

BirdLife Malta has led several campaigns, including efforts to save valleys and ODZs from illegal development, such as 'Wied Żnuber'. They participated in a successful international campaign to adopt the Nature Restoration Law in Europe "which aims to bring back a very small but a very significant amount of nature, which the European continent needs" stated BirdLife Malta (2024). Additionally, they campaigned against Robin and Finch trapping in Malta, which remains illegal under European Union law. BirdLife Malta stated that having solid scientific data, scientific arguments and a good legal team are key to successful campaigns, especially in

court cases. However, their campaign to save the turtle dove is hindered by strong political opposition from the hunting lobby. They suggested that campaigns could be improved with increased creativity, but as an NGO, they are limited by funding constraints, making it costly to hire marketing strategists or promotional companies.

During the interview, BirdLife Malta's representative explained their social media strategy. They use Twitter for political outreach, targeting politicians, MEPs, and the European Commission. Instagram showcases reserve photos, birds, and events, while LinkedIn is utilized for fundraising and sponsorships. TikTok features short videos, and Facebook is used extensively due to its broad age group appeal. In terms of engagement, BirdLife Malta focuses on youths and expats, with a significant membership base from abroad. They tailor their target audience depending on the campaign. For instance, campaigns to protect the turtle dove target older demographics familiar with the issue's history, while initiatives like 'On The Move', promoting bird migration in spring, target families visiting reserves with children (ibid.).

3.2.3 Interview with Friends of the Earth Malta (FoE Malta)

The third interview was with Friends of the Earth Malta. Here the FoE Malta representative emphasized the importance of conserving all species but prioritizing those currently endangered or at risk due to habitat destruction (2024). They referenced the 'Red Data Book' for information on such species. Freshwater species were highlighted as needing more attention due to habitat loss from climate

change and over-extraction of water. Additionally, plants crucial for pollinators and bats were noted as deserving more focus.

The main causes of species endangerment include over-development, habitat loss, pollution from nitrate, pesticides, oil, and plastics in the sea, exploitation of natural resources and introduction of alien species.

“You also have the input of alien species, which can be invasive, so those which create competition. Then we still have a problem of local direct taking from nature. So[,] it could be capturing the birds, it could be cutting or uprooting plants and so on. So[,] there is also that direct threat as well” (Friends of the Earth Malta, 2024).

The interviewee suggested stopping the taking of wild species, protecting remaining natural habitats, reinstating lost habitats, and increasing awareness. They also emphasized the need for government involvement in biodiversity decisions and enhancing enforcement across all levels, which is currently lacking.

Friends of the Earth Malta primarily focuses on pollinator species and plants through campaigns like 'The Bee Cause' and 'Bee Aware', which aim to raise awareness and encourage habitat creation. They've also campaigned to protect freshwater habitats and previously campaigned for the protection of local frogs, turtles, and dolphins, as well as for the inclusion of sites like 'Ta' Ċenc' in Gozo in the Natura 2000 designation. Currently, they are launching a project to raise awareness about local reptile species. Regarding campaigns, FoE Malta's representative highlighted that education is more effective than direct confrontation.

They emphasized the importance of public engagement in nature and noted the effectiveness of using legal tools to hold the government accountable (ibid.).

The interviewee noted the stigma of environmentalists being viewed as extremist minorities, along with people's difficulty in recognizing the interconnectedness of nature.

“[People] don't realise that everything is linked, that ecosystems are very complex and that we depend on them. So many people don't realise how much we depend on them for our own survival. So, people may think it doesn't matter if we lose one species because we have all the others left” (Friends of the Earth Malta, 2024).

The interviewee also mentioned that there is an issue with Speciesism as “some people think that some animals deserve protection more than others because of subjective views on what is cute and what is sweet” (Friends of the Earth Malta, 2024). This often happens with reptiles and bats. The lack of funds poses a challenge for NGOs, particularly when countering large-scale developments by wealthy contractors. Adequate funds are essential to initiate campaigns, which also serve to prevent direct antagonism, vandalism, and threats toward campaigners.

When discussing improvements, the importance of community involvement was highlighted, along with the need for increased use of legal tools, which requires funding. Involving local councils and targeting government officials in campaigns were also mentioned. Friends of the Earth Malta primarily utilizes various social

media platforms, petitions, newsletters, activities, and online letters to ministers or MEPs for their campaign materials. Creativity in campaigning was emphasized, as people are fatigued by negative information, and tailoring approaches to different audiences was noted as important (ibid.).

When asked about environmentally aware social categories, the interviewee noted that Gen X and millennials may be more informed due to growing up during the environmental movement. Youths are expected to be well-informed through their education. Expats, especially in Gozo, volunteer frequently. Conversely, immigrants and those with lower education levels are likely less informed. Regarding target categories, they focus primarily on youth through youth groups, youth worker training, and youth opportunities. They also engage with Gen X, and millennials, and had specific work with refugees. However, they don't actively target expats, who often participate anyway, or individuals with lower education levels, as they are harder to reach (ibid.).

3.2.4 Interview with ACT Malta

The following interview was with ACT Malta, an NGO dedicated to practical and sustainable solutions for environmental, arts, economic, and health issues. They operate a nursery for growing local trees and plants. ACT Malta advocates for prioritizing conservation and awareness of all Maltese species, both indigenous and endemic, considering them integral to the nation's natural heritage. Additionally, they believe Malta has untapped potential for enhancing its natural environment (ACT Malta, 2024).

“Malta has the potential to become a beacon of ecological Mediterranean prosperity. And I believe so for the simple reason that we are a small island state. We're a state. We can decide our own fate and we're insulated. We can manage our environments and habitats in a way that we could adapt and mitigate certain elements of climate change. We're not doing it, yes, but we're still in time. And that would require the conservation and promotion of all native species because of their interrelated relationships” (ACT Malta, 2024).

An interesting fact pointed out during this interview was that the name Malta comes from honey. This meant that we used to have an abundance of honey. Which also meant we had an abundance of flora and biodiversity. Another point mentioned is that the elderly tend to enjoy doing work in nature more than other age groups as there is an element of consequentialism stated ACT Malta (2024).

ACT Malta identifies development as the primary threat to species endangerment due to landscape fragmentation (2024). They also note a lack of local awareness and exposure to nature, contributing to detachment from nature. Additionally, there's a disconnect regarding climate issues and limited awareness of invasive alien species. Examples include Prickly Pear, Fountain Grass, Caster Oil tree, and reeds, which compete with local plants like Fennel, Mastic Tree, Stinking Shumach, and thorny plants on disturbed or degraded land.

Furthermore, there is a noted lack of knowledge about Malta's local environment. During ACT Malta's presentations, when audiences are asked to

name five local trees, most are unable to respond, with some even mentioning fruit trees. This shows that “in regards to the environment in Malta, knowledge is tied in with agriculture, not ecology” (ACT Malta, 2024). Another issue highlighted is the oversight of nature in infrastructure development. For instance, neglecting water management in road construction leads to erosion, as water carries debris towards the sea. ACT (2024) stated that this lack of planning also hinders natural rehabilitation and contributes to rising temperatures due to island development, affecting floral species propagation.

ACT Malta (2024) highlighted the negative environmental impact of shipping mature trees to Malta, posing risks of disease introduction and increasing in carbon footprint, which is counterproductive. They also noted a societal issue where many people express support for causes without providing actual support. This was a realization ACT Malta reached through their own experiences of unmet expectations for support. Protecting species starts with connecting to nature, ACT Malta (2024) believes. They advocate for plant regeneration through propagation and allowing land to self-recover, requiring political will and public pressure. They also noted a lack of knowledge and capabilities in species rehabilitation and challenges in collaborating with landowners.

ACT Malta (2024) finds campaigns often unproductive, as people prefer to buy items rather than fund causes. However, they have had successes, like their campaign on sea waste. Campaigns succeed when targeting those who will act. ACT Malta identified memberships and paid workshops as the best campaigns. Memberships provide funding and legitimize proposals to decision-makers, while

workshops educate individuals about seeds and cuttings. Word of mouth was something which worked well for ACT Malta. They also agreed that creativities in campaigns are helpful. ACT Malta noted that people care more for things they pay for. In their case bought trees thrived, while free ones often died.

Moving on to interest in nature, ACT Malta stated that it is mostly foreigners and expats who show interest (2024). Few locals show interest towards such a cause and the ones who do are mostly farmers. Regards to their target audience ACT Malta targets youths and adults.

3.2.5 Interview with Nature Trust Malta (NTM)

The next interview was with Nature Trust Malta (NTM), which comprises of site managers and volunteers monitoring six sites: 'Il-Ballut ta' Marsaxlokk', 'Il-Magħluq ta' Marsaskala', the Pembroke Natura 2000 site, the 'Iċ-Ċirkewwa' marine area, 'Wied Ollieqa' (protected at a national level), and 'Chadwick Lakes' (protected at a national level). Additionally, they have a Wildlife Rescue group composed of trained volunteers who handle protected fauna, certified with special badges after training by ERA (Nature Trust Malta, 2024).

Nature Trust Malta focuses its campaigns on protecting rare species and habitats. Local protected species include lizards, chameleons, sea turtles, snakes, frogs, hedgehogs, weasels, shrews, and dolphins. They utilize Facebook and Instagram for their campaigns. Currently, they are campaigning to protect the Maltese freshwater crab (il-Qabru) and the 'Killifish' (il-Bużzaqq). They have been advocating for the protection of the 'Killifish' for the past 40-50 years, aiming to have

it recognized as the National Maltese fish due to its rarity and unique habitat in marshlands. According to NTM (2024), local environmental issues include shrews entering houses due to rapid development, snakes facing danger from human attempts to kill them or getting stuck in cans, and freshwater rock pools drying up due to climate change. Farmers sometimes withdraw water from freshwater rock pools which are vital for tadpole populations, as small tadpoles cannot migrate or seek refuge underground like adult frogs.

Local challenges leading to species endangerment include legal and illegal development, habitat reduction, air pollution, and climate change, resulting in decreased rainfall. Trees like the Poplar and White Willow (Żafzafa), dependent on rainfall in valleys, are at risk of destruction due to water shortages. Animals like the Maltese Freshwater Crab and frogs are directly affected by climate change and pollution. Climate change also prompts farmers to extract water from freshwater habitats, as seen in the case of 'Chadwick Lakes', without legal repercussions, endangering local freshwater species (ibid.).

Pollution on land, including litter, traps animals in discarded waste, with even hedgehogs getting caught in plastic. Similarly, litter at sea results in turtles becoming ensnared in abandoned fishing gear like nets and hooks. Additionally, alien species pose a threat by competing with local species. Alien plants, particularly in valleys, outcompete local vegetation, while introduced animal species like crayfish prey on local protected species such as freshwater crabs and tadpoles, endangering their populations stated Nature Trust Malta (2024).

According to the NTM representative (2024), freshwater species deserve more protection due to habitat loss from climate change, while stingrays, facing declining numbers, lack protection. Notably, flora protection hinges on safeguarding local sites since relocation is not feasible. Enhancing enforcement, which is lacking in Malta, is crucial as limited funds allocated to the enforcement of species protection laws exacerbate the issue.

NTM's campaigns focus on education and awareness, handling animals in danger and advocating for species protection like the 'Killifish'. They also engage in cleanups and combatting invasive alien species. NTM (2024) underscored financial limitations hampering campaign quality, resorting to self-taught marketing using tools like Canva. Their campaigns target a broad audience, including youths, although they lack expertise in creating content to do so like videos. Like other NGOs, they rely on volunteers, including foreigners and expats.

3.2.6 Interview with Grow 10 Trees

Grow 10 Trees, a voluntary project initiated by locals was also interviewed. They aim to encourage citizens to grow and nurture 10 local trees for future use in afforestation projects, as stated by their representative (2024). The interviewee emphasized prioritizing conservation and awareness efforts for highly vulnerable species such as the 'White Poplar' and 'Willows' (Żafżafa l-kbira u Żafżafa iż-żgħira), as well as focusing on endangered habitats like sand dunes. The freshwater crab, endangered due to habitat loss, was also mentioned.

Education is crucial for better species protection, emphasized the Grow 10 Trees representative (2024). However, a gap exists between education and action, with environmental education in schools not translating into real-world environmental efforts. Additionally, there's a lack of local appreciation for nature, likely due to many people living in flats without gardens. As the interviewee noted, "Once there is something which you do not have, you will not miss it" (Grow 10 Trees, 2024). Other environmental concerns raised included, the harmful use of pesticides affecting bees, and roadside weed cutting leading to habitat loss.

Grow 10 Trees runs a Facebook page to promote their project and combat local passivity by encouraging tree planting. They organize tree planting events where locally grown trees are planted. However, a noted issue is inadequate post-planting watering, typically managed by contractors assigned by local councils, resulting in tree loss. Grow 10 Trees believes in the importance of community involvement, making people integral to the solution. Similarly to other NGOs, they noted that effective creative marketing requires resources, which volunteers often lack. Regarding environmental interest, they observed that expats are more engaged compared to locals. Grow 10 Trees does not have a specific target audience (ibid.).

3.2.7 Insights from Interviews

In conclusion, these interviews show various issues which harm our local ecosystem along with some good solutions. They also show a good range of local environmental campaigns conducted in Malta and their results. Moreover, they

show information on the local audience's interest in nature, and the audiences targeted by those interviewed.

The interviews highlighted the importance of protecting all native species, with a focus on endangered or rare species. Species needing more attention include the European Turtle Dove, Yelkouan Shearwater, Maltese Freshwater Crab, Killifish, pollinator-friendly plants, bats, stingrays, White Poplar, and Willows. Locally protected species such as lizards, chameleons, sea turtles, snakes, frogs, hedgehogs, weasels, shrews, and dolphins were also noted. Additionally, rare habitats like sand dunes warrant more awareness, with information on endangered species available in the Red Data Book.

The interviews covered various environmental issues contributing to species endangerment, including development, habitat loss, alien species, pollution, climate change, hunting, rat predation, and bycatch. Societal detachment from nature emerged as a significant concern. Factors identified to better protect species include raising awareness of local species, educating on invasive alien species, protecting, and reinstating natural habitats, and enforcing environmental laws. Additional factors include increased funding for enforcement, fostering connectivity to nature, promoting plant regeneration, encouraging environmental activism, and enhancing education.

The past campaigns highlighted by the interviewed environmental organizations addressed a range of topics, including invasive alien species, local habitats, protected species and habitats, birds, freshwater species, pollinator species, and marine waste. Species-specific campaigns targeted the Maltese

freshwater crab, Killifish, local frogs, turtles, dolphins, European turtle dove, Yelkouan Shearwater, Robin, and Finches. Campaigns also targeted specific habitats like marine protected areas, Natura 200 sites, and freshwater habitats. They also addressed development in valleys and advocated for the Nature Restoration Law, species protection, and animal rescue protocols.

Moreover, what worked well in these campaigns was having a theme with good design possibilities, good scientific data and arguments, using an educational approach, and targeting individuals who could act on the matter. Some successful incentives were paid workshops and memberships. One interviewee noted the challenge of explaining technical information, while others suggested that additional funding and legal mechanisms could enhance campaigns. Some interviewees discussed their preferred platforms and materials for campaigns.

Regarding the target audience, Gen X, millennials, youths, and expats were noted as the most environmentally aware, with expats and foreigners showing the most interest in environmental causes. Locals, aside from farmers, showed little interest. Most interviewees targeted youths, adults, or everyone in their campaigns, with only one targeting refugees and none targeting individuals with lower education.

4 Conclusion Advocating for Malta's Threatened Flora

To summarize, the extensive information collected in this study on environmental campaigns will guide designers and NGOs in selecting the most effective visuals and communication techniques. It culminates in an exemplary project that integrates this knowledge into a creative initiative tailored for the Maltese Islands. This project also fulfils the aim of producing more purposeful design work.

The literature review revealed that combining images with text is most effective in environmental campaigns, with photographs perceived as truthful. Additionally, evoking sadness and reducing psychological distance can significantly boost public support. Various communication techniques can enhance the effectiveness of environmental campaigns, with audience research being crucial for success. The literature review also highlighted that effective use of semiotics is essential for achieving desired outcomes. These insights align with this study, offering a compilation of best practices and existing research for curating successful environmental campaigns.

Moving forward with the methodology, through the conducted case studies, quite a good range of points came out. The first one was that creativity within a campaign is essential to capture your audience's attention. This is because creative concepts leave a bigger impact on the audience, as they are more memorable. Another point was that visual style and tone should reflect the concept's purpose, and be curated for the chosen target audience. Furthermore, it was found that humour is a good method of grabbing the attention of youths. It is also good to use

multiple platforms such as print, out-of-home and social media for your campaign to reach a wide audience. Creating branded accessories was found to be a great way to raise funds for the initiative in concern. Lastly, including a call to action, such as supporting the campaign by purchasing merchandise or signing a petition, was found to be beneficial.

During the interviews, several points were mentioned. One of them was the importance of protecting all native species, particularly endangered or threatened ones with rare habitats. Key threats to species include development, habitat loss, alien species, pollution, and climate change, with additional concerns like habitat alteration and fragmentation. It was mentioned that information on endangered species is available in the Red Data Book. Some effective protection measures mentioned included increasing awareness of local flora and fauna, educating about invasive species, and protecting and restoring natural habitats. Past campaigns of environmental organizations have focused on invasive species, local habitats, and protected species; finding success with strong design, scientific data, educational approaches, and targeted efforts, including incentives like paid workshops and memberships. Interviewees suggested that more funds and legal mechanisms could further enhance campaigns. Environmental awareness is highest among Gen X, millennials, youths, and expats, with expats showing the most interest and volunteerism. Campaigns typically target youths and adults, with little focus on refugees or individuals with lower education levels.

Through the case studies design and communication concepts in creating environmental campaigns were extracted. Through the interviews, information on

threatened species, environmental concerns, local environmental campaigns, and their targeted audiences was gathered. All this information was essential in learning how to curate a successful species awareness campaign in Malta. Through this process, it was also found that there is a lack of true appreciation of Malta's nature. Furthermore, not many campaigns on local threatened fauna were conducted and it seemed like none of the few focused on their connection to Maltese heritage. Thus, it was decided to focus this dissertation's project on the connection between Maltese threatened flora and Maltese heritage.

The project, Blossoms of Heritage features six intricately designed tiles portraying plant species of a threatened status, akin to traditional Maltese tiles. Each tile is accompanied by a supporting postcard providing species information, serving as both a celebration of their beauty and a call to action for preservation. This project serves as a reminder that just like traditional Maltese tiles, local plant species are part of our heritage and emphasize the urgent need for environmental conservation efforts.

For future recommendations, more research could be conducted on the semiotics and frameworks in environmental visuals. How the use of visuals differs in each environmental topic and which semiotics and framework as best suited for which topic and audiences can also be further explored. There can also be more research on which types of visual mediums different age groups and societal groups prefer.

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Appendices

Interview with Friends of the Earth Malta

Abigail Farrugia

Good morning, I am Abigail Farrugia, and I am making my dissertation on environmental campaigns and local species in Malta. My first question to you is which category of local species do you think needs more conservation and awareness right now? local flora, local fauna, or local insects?

Annalise Falzon

I think it is a very big question and very difficult to answer as I would always automatically choose everything because it is very difficult to pinpoint. If I had to pinpoint, I would say I would have to prioritise those which are considered endangered or currently at risk. Or else, those whose habitat is being destroyed more rapidly, maybe than others. But I would say you cannot pick because it is all a system as we know.

Abigail Farrugia

What are the main causes of species endangerment?

Annalise Falzon

So for Malta, it is overdevelopment, which leads to habitat destruction. So, the loss of habitat is one of the biggest issues and if a habitat is not completely lost, you still have habitat alteration, so habitats are changed, habitats are fragmented

and that reduces the biodiversity and the health of the system in general. And then you can add other factors which are pollutants which can be anything from if we are speaking on land from nitrate, pesticide runoff and so on. If you're in the sea, could be oil, plastics and all the other pollutants you know of.

You also have the input of alien species, which can be invasive, so those which create competition. Then we still have a problem of local direct taking from nature. So, it could be capturing the birds, it could be cutting or uprooting plants and so on. So, there is also that direct threat as well.

Abigail Farrugia

Do you have any information on currently which species needs more protection and why?

Annalise Falzon

So I think again the ones which have already been listed in the Red Data book because of being endangered or at risk.

If I had to think of a particular category now, I would think a lot about freshwater species because we are seeing a rapid change in climate and a lot of these habitats are drying up. Even because of over-extraction by humans of fresh water. So, I think freshwater species would be on the top of my list, and then any plants which provide food to all pollinator species.

And if I think of land animals, I think of bats because they have not been given enough attention. But as I said again, I think they all need protection because the habitats of all of them are being threatened.

Abigail Farrugia

And what do you think should be done to protect these species better?

Annalise Falzon

First thing, I think the most obvious would be that the taking of any wild species needs to be stopped immediately. But there are already laws for most of them, so that should be enforced. But very, very important would be habitat protection. So, any habitats that we have been left unprotected need to be protected fully. If habitats have been lost, they need to be reinstated at the earliest possible because habitat restoration takes a very, very long time. So, we cannot afford to lose more. Together with this, you need to have a lot and a lot of enforcement which has been missing. So, enforcement on all levels. And I would say we need more awareness now, not just with the public but with all government sectors that may be involved in making decisions for our biodiversity.

Abigail Farrugia

What are some campaigns you and other NGOs have done regarding conservation and protecting local species in the past?

Annalise Falzon

OK, so as Friends of the Earth Malta there has always been a lot of focus on pollinator species and pollinator plants. And so, there were campaigns on bees, but not only. There was The Bee Cause campaign and the Be Aware, both involved in increasing awareness training but also creating small habitats for pollinators and encouraging people to create more spaces like that.

More recent things I can think of are, the campaign of protecting freshwater habitats in Tal-Wej, which was hopefully successful, but we're still waiting to see what happens there. In the past, I've been involved now since the early 90s, so I can think of many campaigns, for instance about the frogs when they were still not protected. As nature trust, at the time we had, there were campaigns on turtles and dolphins because they were not protected until 1993.

There was also a lot of campaigning when Natura 2000 sites were being designated and created. There was for instance, I would say very important things about sites which had been left out. So, for instance, ta' Ċenċ in Gozo had been left out of the designated sites and we managed to get it included. Then I can think of specific species like the hedgehog, and some more awareness about hedgehogs. The Abro, the freshwater crab. Now with Friends of the Earth Malta, we are starting a project which will focus on reptiles and creating more awareness

around reptiles in Malta. And then of course there are NGOs like BirdLife who have done massive campaigns on so many bird species in Malta.

Abigail Farrugia

What do you think worked well within these campaigns and why?

Annalise Falzon

So I think the most campaigns which were more successful always had an element of education and awareness, rather than direct confrontation. I would say also involving the people's own feeling of nature connection. So, you people need to be involved to care about something, so that is always very important.

In other cases, there was more because of campaigns' direct involvement of government entities so that they take responsibility, but also to ensure that their own legislation would be enforced. There were times when legal tools were used in campaigns and those were successful because we already had quite good legislation, but there was no enforcement. So, it is basically bringing the government to be responsible also for its own legislation.

Abigail Farrugia

And what do you think? Did not work so well and why?

Annalise Falzon

I think one main issue has always been, that environmentalists in Malta, at least let's say that is how it was in the 90s, I think it is still a bit, are seen as extremists as a particular sector of the public as a minority. And so, they're often treated in this way like sort of, ok, the extremists, they want to stop development there. It is as if any environmentalist is against the economic structure of the country and so on. So, there's often the stereotypical view of what an environmentalist is, and we do not realise that everybody needs to be an environmentalist. Immediately, like we cannot afford not to be environmentalists.

Having said that, I see that many people struggle to see the links in nature. They do not realise that everything is linked, that ecosystems are very complex and that we depend on them. So many people do not realise how much we depend on them for our own survival. So, people may think it does not matter if we lose one species because we have all the others left. And so, I think it is often a matter of not being ignorant about some things really.

Also, the fact of Speciesism, so for instance, some people think that some animals deserve protection more than others because of subjective views on what is cute and what is sweet. But maybe others are not. I see this a lot with bats and reptiles for instance. And then I would also say, in some cases, lack of funds was always a problem because you must often counteract in the case of big developments, you must counteract contractors who work with millions of euros.

So, you really need more funds to get a proper campaign going and to avoid as much as possible, direct antagonism, which has often resulted in vandalism or threats, being suffered by the campaigners themselves.

Abigail Farrugia

How could these campaigns be improved in the future?

Annalise Falzon

It really is necessary to be in communities together. It's no longer a matter of 1 environmentalist group getting together with another group and that's it, the same people. It's a matter now of really if you want to, have any green space around you, we are not speaking out of complex habitats, even in a green space, we must get communities together.

I think we need to use more legal tools so that has not been exploited enough. But legal tools require funds because you must fight battles in court. I would say getting local councils involved is necessary because many councils do not have the right awareness. And for every government department, I think we need to have campaigns which direct also all the ones making decisions and all the ones who are taking care of our legislation and so on. So maybe in some cases, we directed more towards the public. But we're seeing more and more that it needs to be government officials who need to become more aware, and I would also say

this would be good to have more crowdfunding as well even especially for any legal battles that need to be done.

Abigail Farrugia

And within your campaigns what materials and platforms do you use?

Annalise Falzon

In the present, it is always mainly social media could be online petitions or sending online letters directly to ministers for instance, or MEPs. So, for instance, 2 years ago there was a European-wide campaign to save the bees and farmers, and that was a European collective initiative. There was a platform there, but everybody could also collect petitions by hand in the traditional way, but it was like a joint effort between countries, which was successful in the end. So different social media is always important.

We use our newsletter, of course, a lot. And I would say through our activities, we are always passing a message. So even if it is not a direct campaign, there is always campaigning going on, even if it is not like you know, a campaign focusing on bees. There is always that message in our activities. So, we are always working in line with what we believe in.

Abigail Farrugia

The campaign curated more creatively, could boost the campaign?

Annalise Falzon

Yes, I think we're seeing the need for this because people are fed up with being told about negative things, for instance. So, we need to find other ways. And I think find ways of directing it towards wider sectors as well. So yes, I think there is quite a bit to be done in that way. But you need to have somehow different approaches if you are working with different sectors. So, if you are working with youths, it is going to be very different than working with the government officials or working with the local councils.

Abigail Farrugia

How interested and informed are individuals of these social categories regarding environmental issues? Youths (15 to 25), Gen X and millennials (35 to 50), persons over 50, immigrants, expats, and individuals with a lower education.

Annalise Falzon

I am sure there was some research done on this, especially amongst youths and their awareness in Malta and a European-wide survey was done. Now I do not know. It is difficult for me to say. I have never done my own research on this. I think Generation X and millennials have grown up when there was more of the environment movement gaining momentum. So, I think in some aspects they may

be more aware. On the other hand, the youths have had the benefit of having it included a lot in their school system. Maybe we did not have that in our age. Education for sustainable development is now incorporated in all curriculums. So, I would say youth should be quite well informed on most issues. I say should be because I do not always see that. Logically I would think that they should be some of the more aware.

Expats it depends on maybe which countries they come from. But let us say for instance in Gozo there has always been this trend, the trend of foreign volunteers doing a lot of work. And they tend to be expats volunteering for heritage protection and so on.

The other groups, individuals with low education and immigrants I think would be on the lower part of the list in the case of immigrants. Again, it depends on where they are coming from. But often, if they are immigrants seeking to find a better place, they may be more focused now on improving their conditions or their survival, of course. Individuals with low education, I think that is a difficult area because it is very difficult to reach them, I would say.

Abigail Farrugia

Which from the previously mentioned social categories, do you target most in your campaigns and how?

Annalise Falzon

I think we are focusing a lot recently more on youth. On youth groups and both by training youth workers, but also by having opportunities for youths. As you know, the youth hub with possible exchanges with giving them more opportunities to learn in informal situations or gardening and so on, rather than in a formal set-up. So, youths are high on our list, I would say.

Then maybe the second would be the Gen X and millennials. Maybe they have grown up with the idea, but they still see things have not changed, so then maybe we manage to engage more of this group I would say in our activities. There has also been some work with immigrants specifically with refugees, for instance. So, we have had some activities which are specifically directed to them. Expats, not directly, because expats tend to attend activities in general, in any case.

Individuals with a low education, I think as I said before, this is a sector we still need to improve upon, and it is difficult to find. Maybe we still have to find a way to do that.

Abigail Farrugia

OK. That is it for the interview. Thank you for your time.

Annalise Falzon

Thank you.

Abigail Farrugia

Have a good day.

Annalise Falzon

Thank you and good luck with your research. Let us know how it goes, OK?

Abigail Farrugia

Thank you. Thank you so much.

Sample Questionnaires

Synopsis

Hi, I am Abigail Farrugia a final year student at the Institute for the Creative Arts studying Graphic Design. I am currently working on my dissertation study which focuses on environmental campaigns. An environmental campaign aims at changing public perceptions and behaviours on an ecological issue. This study explores the visuals, techniques and frameworks used in environmental campaigns. It aims to find the most effective methods to create an environmental campaign to conserve local wildlife on the Maltese islands.

I would like to conduct an online interview with you to gather information regarding local species and environmental campaigns. Would you be okay with that? If so, when would you be available?

Interview Questions:

1. Which category of local species do you think needs more conservation and awareness? Local fauna, local flora or local insects?
2. What are the main causes of this category of species' endangerment?
3. Which specific species needs more protection and why?
4. What should be done to protect these species better?
5. What are some campaigns you and other NGOs have done regarding conserving and protecting local species in the past?
6. What do you think worked well in these campaigns and why?
7. What do you think did not work well and why?
8. How could these campaigns be improved in the future?
9. Do you think having the campaign curated more creatively way could boost the campaign?
10. How interested and informed are individuals in these social categories regarding environmental issues?
 - a. Youths (15-25)
 - b. Gen X and Millennials (35-50)
 - c. Persons over 50
 - d. Immigrants
 - e. Expats
 - f. Individuals with a low education
11. Which of the previously mentioned social categories do you target in your campaigns? And how?